

New Technology Adoption and Artisans' Output in Akure, Ondo State, South West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research aims to determine how new technology use affects artisans' output in Akure, Ondo State, and Southwest Nigeria. What perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived trust, and facilitating conditions affect artisans' output, and whether behavioral intention mediated between these variables and artisans' output. This study used a survey design method, which relies on primary data. Three hundred fifty respondents were selected at random using a self-administered questionnaire. The descriptive statistics were determined using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), while Smart PLS V4.0.8.5 was used to calculate the quantitative research inferential statistics. This study supported earlier theoretical perspectives to create a new conceptual framework. It also endorsed the modified framework because the results showed a substantial correlation between the endogenous and exogenous variables. The study, however, suggested that the government need to implement mechanisms to supply new tools, engage in technology transfer from developed nations, and compel money deposit institutions to lend to artisans.

Keywords: Perceived usefulness, Perceived ease of use, Facilitating conditions, Behavioural intention, output

Introduction

The prosperity of the world has been predicted to be spurred by technology. It evolves without limit to the ability to achieve in all facets of life. Technology has also come of age. The use of technologies has highlighted high-yield production from the stone age through the Medieval era and into the modern era. Despite their limited production scope, artisan belongs to the industrial sector, often referred to as small business enterprises. The discovery of steam engines triggered the first Industrial Revolution, industrial mass production ignited the second, and the digital and electronic revolutions spurred the third. By bringing technology to alter physical and biological materials, the fourth industrial revolution will obfuscate the boundaries between the digital, biological, and physical realities (Skilton & Hovsepian, 2017).

Since human beings resist change, this can be said of the adoption of new technologies by artisans, who form the buck of the population under investigation. Before the discovery of innovative technology, it took some time for new methods to be accepted by people, incorporated into social norms and traditions, and become commonplace. Any artisan is highly localized and has always been fitted to its community, a trait that additive manufacturing technologies offer (Li, 2017).

Cuvelier (2011) emphasizes that advanced economies are proudly celebrated with intelligent technologies in the informal sector, where artisans are largely populated. Surprisingly, it is a different issue in third-world countries where artisans are gabbling for survival using obsolete equipment inherited from their forebears. John-Nsa (2021) confirms that vulcanizers, mechanics, tailors, welders, painters, bricklayers, hairdressers, barbers, and the like, who work in the informal sector are found throughout the streets of Nigerian cities, towns, and villages in informal settlements of Enugu City, Nigeria. Despite receiving little acknowledgment from the government, they are economically productive. Their ability to produce is frequently underestimated due to limited literacy (Agbolade, 2014).

The main objective of this research is to evaluate how technology has affected artisans' output despite the government's full contempt for the sector and its economic importance. The specific objectives are to ascertain how the use of new technology affects their output regarding perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived trust, facilitating conditions, and whether behavioural intention mediated between these variables and artisans' output.

This study was prompted by the abundance of technology adoption submissions from multiple studies that lacked any analysis of the implications for artisan production. Scholars' numerous findings on technology adoption did not address its effects on the productivity of artisans. This study would look into the gap between previous studies' findings and whether or not new technology hampers artisans' output.

The lack of innovative technology has hampered the productivity of artisans in the study area. This was supported by Onyancha (2021), who claimed to have examined the degree of technological adoption by Kenyan craftspeople while producing leather goods. The researcher visited several Kenyan Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and artisans who make leather goods in urban areas. It was discovered that these groups had relatively low levels of technology use. This was brought on by a number of issues, including a lack of funding to purchase cutting-edge technology and machinery, a lack of technical expertise (human resources), and a lack of government assistance. This study was also prompted by the researchers' familiarity with the subject and proximity to the study area.

Review of Literature

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) of Davis (1989), the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) of Rogers (1995), the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) of Ajzen (1985), the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) by Venkatesh et al. (2003) were the most widely used theories of technology adoption. With the theories mentioned

above, this study examined how the adoption of new technologies affects the output of artisans. These theories have made significant efforts to integrate a variety of independent variables that allow researchers to conclude analyses to explain user's behaviour and the adoption of new technology. The TAM and UTAUT will be used in this study because many scholars frequently use them, and are still relevant to modern investigations. UTAUT has often been employed by researchers in their research due to its greater capacity for thoroughness and explanation (Patil et al., 2020).

Vimal, Amilan & Apama (2023) assert that the TAM examines a user's readiness to adopt various forms of technology. It was formed from TRA. TAM popularised the idea of behavioural intention based on the intention with the potential to predict acceptance. Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitude toward usage, intention to use, and actual use are among the themes of TAM. Because of TAM's simplicity, several researchers have used it, which also applies in this study to assess the effects on artisans' output. It is not a misplaced priority not to include perceived risk and trust as they relate to this research population.

Venkatesh et al. (2003) created UTAUT by fusing a variety of theories related to technology adoption. New constructs, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, and behavioural intention to use technology were developed as a result of their research. Other hedonistic motivational, monetary, and habitual components were studied in the UTAUT2. The useful dimensions from both TAM and UTAUT will be combined for the objectives of this investigation.

The researchers of this study decided to eliminate superfluous aspects, including social impact, hedonistic motive, and habit, after evaluating the TAM, UTAUT, and UTAUT2 dimensions because they were not crucial to the study. The artisans under investigation were examined separately, not collectively. The pleasure motive has no place in this study, and their habit regarding the adoption of technologies is irrelevant. The investigation's crucial focus is to ascertain how artisans use new technologies to advance the quality of their work rather than for personal pleasure.

Egesi (2016) concluded that artisanal fishermen in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, can significantly enhance their output by utilizing new technologies. The importance of adopting new technologies is indisputable when anticipating artisans to increase production. Akani (2008) found that motorized fishing (MF) is more effective than manual propulsion fishing (MPF) in a different study. Even though MF produced a greater harvest than MPF, the researcher advised that the technical proficiency of the MF operators might be increased through better fishing instruction and prompt credit facility supply to purchase the required fishing equipment and materials.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT), inclined artisans, according to Omotayo & Babalola (2016), are now an essential component of society. Examining this study regarding the social exchange and social capital theory also sheds light on the artisans' social context and knowledge-sharing behaviour (KSB), the study supports using social exchange and social capital theories to explain people's actions while sharing knowledge (KS). It was discovered that KSB and perceived benefit, social affiliation, common language, and goals had significant connections. The correlation

between these variables suggests the significance of these elements as requirements for the adoption of KS by artisans, unlike the semi-literate artisans who are the primary subject of the investigation of Omotayo & Babalola's (2016) study, conducted among literate ICT artisans in Ibadan, Southwest Nigeria.

The empirical review of many works shows several scholars concur that economic, social, and environmental factors all play a role in how industrial technology is adopted (Marcon, Soliman, Gerstlberger, & Frank, 2022; Arnold, Veile, & Voigt, 2018). Every component has a unique level of influence. The use of technology by various artisans led to an uneven level of quality in the souvenir items made from coconut trash, as evident in the study of Dumasari, Budiningsih, Darmawan, & Santosa (2017) to examine the existence of several factors that determine the power of the adoption of production technology on micro souvenirs creative enterprise, Indonesia.

In their study on Kenyan leather product manufacturing processes, Onyanha & Peters (2019) found that none of the enterprises had used soft technology, while just 6% had used hard technology, which involved machines. The main explanation for the low technology adoption rate was financial constraints. Others include a lack of technical proficiency, poor commitment from senior management, and competitiveness.

In the study of Adejuwon, Taiwo, and Ilori (2014) on encouraging technology adoption in the small-scale oil palm fruit processing industry in Southwest Nigeria, it was discovered that new technologies had not been successfully adopted into the sector. The informal sector includes producers and artisans, who develop small-scale technologies for two stages of the oil palm fruit processing, embracing the doing, utilizing, and interacting modes of learning and invention. These technologies, developed by the unorganized sector of the system, have been widely adopted by the business community and are typically based on cost cuts and replication. For craftsmen and artisans to perform at their best, Isife & Akpen-Ade (2021) reiterated the need for training.

According to Alfred & Archie (2016), the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) was established in 1986 due to the high unemployment rate in the 1980s. NDE was given the power to develop both short-term and long-term plans to lower Nigeria's unemployment rate by Decree 24 of 1989. The core mandate of NDE includes: designing and implementing programs to combat mass unemployment; articulating policies aimed at developing work programs with labour-intensive potentials; obtaining and maintaining a data bank on employment and vacancies in the country to act as a clearing house to link job seekers with vacancies in collaboration with other government agencies; and to implement any other policies as may be laid down from time to time by the Board established under sections of the enabling Act (National Directorate of Employment Annual Report, 2018). Despite the artisanal self-organized structure in every corner of the nation, the NDE has come under criticism or pressure for being unable to collect accurate data on them. However, NDE produced data on training where only a few tools were available to the trainees (Alfred & Archie, 2016).

The operationalizations of the independent and dependent variables, which were taken from TAM and UTAUT by different scholars and published in journal articles, focus on this work's

objectives. The original research on TAM and UTAUT formed the conceptual framework of this research. Hence, the framework is shown in Figure 1. They study adopted the constructs of perceived usefulness (PU), also known as performance expectancy (PE), perceived ease of use (PEOU), also known as effort expectancy (EE), perceived trust (PT), and facilitating conditions (FC), which serve as independent variables. These constructs are based on prior research from which the theoretical framework for the TAM and UTAUT models was developed. Both endogenous and exogenous variables are done by behavioural intention, whereas the dependent variable is output (OP). The variables are mediated by behavioral intention (Sugandini, Rahatmawati, & Istanto, 2012).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Adapted TAM and UTAUT model

The objective of TAM is to apply new technology in a way that will be most beneficial (Davis, 1989). It correlates with how to maximize output using the latest technology, which was previously impossible with outdated technology. UTAUT's performance expectancy, which measures how strongly a person believes deploying new technology would enhance output (Venkatesh et al. 2003), shows a person's desire to use new technology as long as it meets the desired need better. With the use of modern technologies, the output of the craftspeople would be abundant. So, this null hypothesis was put forth.

Ho₁: The output of artisans is unaffected by the perceived usefulness of new technology adoption.

The term "perceived ease of use" refers to how straightforwardly the new technology would be implemented to maximize production. This goes hand in hand with UTAUT's effort expectation, which measures how simple it is to adopt new technologies (Rogers, 1995; Venkatesh et al., 2003). Due to people's natural resistance to change, artisans can have a fear of using new technologies. Artisans have the impression that new technologies might be challenging to use. For many researchers who claimed that attitude and intention to accept technology are significantly influenced by perceived ease of use, the time it takes to become comfortable with the usage and understand it also accounts for it (Wong & Teo, 2009). Hence the null hypothesis is formulated:

Ho₂: The output of artisans is unaffected by the perceived ease of use of new technology adoption.

Perceived trust, in this context, refers to the possibility of satisfaction arising from applying new technologies. A belief in the latest technology's ability to produce the best results would drive artisans

to look for ways to upgrade and resolve to buy more to increase productivity. For instance, a bricklayer would be exposed to innovative Chinese block molding and wall plastering equipment, which, when used, would reduce energy sapping and save time. In turn, this will improve his performance in the shortest possible time. It is anticipated that using new technology may result in inevitable glitches, which could impact output. Rouse (2015) asserts that, technically speaking, a glitch is a minor, transient malfunction that happens in a system for unclear reasons. Even when the root cause of a glitch is dark, it can seriously harm the system, leading to power outages, brief service interruptions, or data loss. The null hypothesis is, therefore, formulated:

Ho₃: The output of artisans is unaffected by the perceived trust of new technology adoption.

Facilitating conditions refer to the extent to which one thinks that a favourable environment determines maximum production (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Conditions in third-world nations influence how quickly artisans will adopt new technologies. The new technology that has been acquired must be powered by a steady energy source. Government tax laws ought to be moderately strict because that would defeat the purpose of acquisition. Compared to other factors like job satisfaction, work-life balance, and health while it is being carried out in a conducive environment, Ratnar & Kaur's (2016) study showed that job performance is the most influenced element with the introduction of information technology. Therefore, the null hypothesis is formulated:

Ho₄: The output of artisans is unaffected by facilitating conditions of new technology adoption.

Many scholars have suggested that behavioural intention is the best predictor of adopting technology. According to the research of Ajzen (1991); Fishbein & Ajzen (1977) in TRA, beliefs influence attitudes, and attitudes reflect the nature of the intentions that regulate behavioural usage. TAM clarifies the impact of behavioural intention, which is the aspect of behaviour that can be anticipated with the most significant degree of significance. A mediating factor between the endogenous and exogenous variables in this study is thought to be behavioural intention. Hence, the null hypothesis is formulated thus:

Ho₅: The output of artisans is not mediated by the behavioural intention of new technology adoption.

Methodology

This study adopted the survey research technique for extrapolating from a sample to a population and coming to generalizations about the entire population (Khong, 2005). The population comprises five hundred and thirty (530) skilled artisans randomly investigated in Akure, Ondo State. The study area was chosen because it is accessible to the researchers. Random sampling technique was adopted to ensure the sample result closely matches the entire population. (Shadish, Cook, & Campbell, 2002). A structured questionnaire was used as the instrument to gather data. The study employed a quantitative analysis method of a Seven-Points Likert scale for a thorough grasp of the research questions raised. In the scale of the instrument, 1 denotes Strongly Disagree (SD), 2 depicts Disagree (D), 3 indicates Moderately Disagree (MD), 4 signifies Neutral (N), 5 describes Moderately Agree (MA), 6 represents

Agree (A), and 7 means Strongly Agree (SA). The internal consistency, construct validity, and user acceptability of a 7-point Likert scale are superior to other Likert scales. This argument is also supported by a broad array of studies by Abdurrahaman, Owusu, & Soladoye (2018) and Abdurrahaman & Owusu (2020). The SmartPLS V4.0.8.5 was used for inferential statistics, and SPSS was employed to analyze the descriptive statistics.

Table 1: Variables and Question Items

Constructs and Questions

Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)

PEOU1: It would be simple to learn how to use my new tool.

PEOU2 Using the new tool to perform what I want it to do would be easy for me.

PEOU3: It would be simple for me to carry out more tasks with my new tool.

PEOU4: The new tool would be simple to use for more output.

Perceived Usefulness (PU)

PU1: I could complete jobs more rapidly using the new tool.

PU2: My work performance would increase if I used the new tool.

PU3: My productivity would increase if I used the new tool.

PU4: The new tool would be helpful to me in my work.

Perceived Trust (PT)

PT1: I have faith that the new instrument will not disappoint me.

Pt2: With the new instrument, the likelihood of a good outcome would influence my work.

Pt3: My output would increase due to my trust in the new tool.

Facilitating Conditions (FC)

FC1: Everything I need to use with the new tool is available.

FC2: The new tool is compatible with the existing ones I already use.

FC3: The improved conditions have led to an increase in my output.

Behavioural Intention (BI)

BI1: I would use the new tool if I could access it.

BI2: My behavioural intention to use the new tool would increase my output.

BI3: In the future, I want to employ another new tool to raise my output.

Output (OP)

OP1: I find that when I use the new tool, my output increases.

OP2: Using the new tool improves my perception of its usefulness, which boosts my output.

OP3: My new tool facilitating circumstance enhances my productivity.

Op4: My output increases as a result of perceived tool trust.

Source: Corritore, C. L., Kracher, B., & Wiedenbeck, S. (2003); (Davis, 1989, p. 340, p. 340); (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008, p. 314; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

Eight different categories of skilled artisans served as respondents. A total of 530 questionnaires were analyzed, with a response rate of 98.15%. Five hundred and forty copies of the questionnaires were returned after being filled out, and ten were discarded because they were not properly filled.

An overwhelming 72.6% of respondents were men, compared to just 27.4% of women. 39.8% and 33.8% of the respondents were between the productive ages of 31-40 and 41-50. First-degree holders comprised 31.3% and National Diploma holders comprised 36.4%, while auto mechanics were first with 22.8% and barbers with 15.5% as seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Demography of respondents

Variable	Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	385	72.6
	Female	145	27.4
Age	21 – 30	58	10.9
	31 – 40	211	39.8
	41 – 50	179	33.8
	50 – 60	82	15.5
Education	M.Sc	26	4.9
	B.Sc	166	31.3
	ND	193	36.4
	O/L	145	27.4
Skill	Barber	82	15.5
	Carpenter	46	8.7
	Hair Stylist	68	12.8
	Auto Mechanic	121	22.8
	Painter	47	8.9
	Tailor	70	13.2
	Vulcaniser	66	12.5
	Welder	30	5.7

Data Analysis

Two separate analyses of the descriptive statistics using SmartPLS v4.0.8.5 are required. First, the evaluation of the measurement equation model, and second, the assessment of the structural equation model. These are summarised below in Tables 3, 4, 5, & 6, and Figures 2 & 3, respectively (Hair et al., 2022).

Table 3: Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
BI	0.521	0.527	0.757	0.510
FC	0.590	0.584	0.777	0.538
OP	0.764	0.769	0.850	0.587
PEOU	0.852	0.861	0.901	0.695
PT	0.934	0.934	0.958	0.883
PU	0.845	0.852	0.895	0.681

Internal consistency of >0.700 can be regarded as "acceptable," according to Hair et al. (1998). Other values in Cronhach's Alpha and Composite reliability (rho_c) are >0.700, except the lower values of BI (0.521) and FC (0.590). Furthermore, each AVE value is above the 0.500 threshold as suggested to be acceptable by Hair et al., Black, et al.(2010); Ofori et al. (2018), as shown in Table 3.

Figure 2: Algorithm sequence SmartPLS V4.0.8.5

Figure 3: Bootstrapping sequence SmartPLS

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	t statistics (O/STDEV)	p values
BI -> OP	0.479	0.482	0.040	11.877	0.000
FC -> BI	0.256	0.259	0.039	6.623	0.000
PEOU -> BI	0.212	0.211	0.047	4.486	0.000
PT -> BI	0.166	0.164	0.040	4.125	0.000
PU -> BI	0.223	0.224	0.040	5.530	0.000

Table 4 displays the results of the structural equation model at a 5% level of significance for testing the null hypotheses that have been proposed.

Table 5: Relationship between Endogenous and Exogenous Variables

Hypothesis	Relationship	t value	p-value	Decision	2.5%	97.5%
Ho1	PU->BI	5.530**	0.000	Rejected	0.144	0.302
Ho2	PEOU->BI	4.486**	0.000	Rejected	0.119	0.301
Ho3	PT->BI	4.125**	0.000	Rejected	0.086	0.243
Ho4	FC->BI	6.623**	0.000	Rejected	0.183	0.335
Ho5	BI->PO	11.877**	0.000	Rejected	0.398	0.558

*p<0.05, **p<0.01

Table 6: Model fit

Construct	R ²	R ² adjusted	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
BI	0.398	0.393	0.363	0.804	0.613
OP	0.199	0.197	0.092	0.958	0.764

SRMR: Saturated=0.086, Estimated=0.093

Results and Discussion of Findings

The link between the endogenous variables and the independent variables, as shown in Tables 4 & 5, suggests that artisans are increasingly productive with adopting new technologies, which was in line with the study's objectives. The behavioural intention serves as mediation between the variables. The Ho₁ with $\beta=0.224$, $t=5.530$, and $p=0.000$ indicated a statistically significant association. Therefore, Ho₁ is rejected because respondents indicated they would produce more after acquiring new technologies because of their perceived utility. The value on Ho₂ is statistically significant, which displays $\beta=0.211$, $t=4.486$, and $p=0.000$. Considering that craftsmen anticipate that perceived ease of use concerning behavioural intention will increase production, the null hypothesis is likewise rejected. Ho₃ with $\beta=0.164$, $t=4.125$, and $p=0.000$ also nullified the null hypothesis over the confirmation of artisans of perceived trust on behavioural intention to adopt new technology which would enhance their output. The artisans show that they have improved output with behavioural intention to use new technologies under favourable conditions. This was shown in the statistical relevance of Ho₄ with $\beta=0.259$, $t=6.623$, and $p=0.000$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Regarding the artisans' behavioural intention to other constructs, many scholars confirmed the influence of it in their numerous studies (Patil et al., 2020; Venkatesh et al., 2003; Davis, 1989; Gupta & Gupta, 2008; AbuShanah, 2007; Dasgupta, 2008; Catherine et al., 2017). The connection between output and behavioural intention has invalidated the invalid speculation of BI->PO with $\beta=0.482$, $t=11.877$, and $p=0.000$ in Ho₅. This demonstrates that with the blend of a multitude of constructs with the intervening job of BI, artisans' degree of output would be upgraded. The rejection of all of the null hypotheses amply demonstrates the study's objectives. When all the exogenous variables are suitably prevailing, the endogenous variable will increase.

In Table 6, following the advice of Henseler et al. (2016), the predictive validity was explained using R². The thresholds of 0.75 are viewed as higher, 0.50 as moderate, and 0.25 as weak. Raithel et al. (2012) reiterate 0.10 value of R² is satisfactory. Likewise, Q² is a proportion of the prescient meaning of the endogenous variable. The value is >0, which is thought of as good. Hair et al. (2019) state that Q² esteem is more noteworthy than zero recommends sufficient recreation, and the model is prescient. In this review, the OP, which is the essential variable, is thought of as prescient of other factors on the grounds that R² = 0.199 and Q² = 0.092, respectively.

Notwithstanding, scholars contend that model fit is less helpful in PLS-SEM dissimilar to in the CB-SEM where it is fundamental (Hair, 2019). Westland (2015) declared that model fit had delivered PLS-SEM incapable of speculation testing and affirmation. Meanwhile, the SRMR for this study is:

saturated = 0.086 and estimated = 0.093. The limit is somewhere in the range of 0 and 0.08 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). Consequently, the model fit of this study is significant.

Conclusion

This study examined the impacts of innovation reception on artisans' output in Akure, Ondo State. The interceding job of behavioural intention between the endogenous and exogenous factors highlights the essential commitments of gaining advancements corresponding to extreme productivity. New technology adoption is considered to be ingrained daily, which sheds light on how it affects productivity and the efficacy and efficiency of industrial processes. This is shown in the study on mechanical cotton spinning by Juhász, Squicciarini, & Voigtländer (2020). It was decided that it would take some time for the advantages of new technology to become apparent since firms would need to learn how to use it successfully once it had gained general use. Similar analogies have been made between technology's slow adoption and poor productivity. The reflection of the underlying technology and the efficiency with which the specific technology is implemented both affect the volume of production.

Restrictions to this study range from the education worth of respondents who could experience issues addressing a few inquiries precisely. But it does not discredit the result of the discoveries as sizeable numbers of respondents were well depended upon to address the inquiries accurately. Likewise, the numbers of respondents are tiny, contrasted with the metropolitan nature of the area being scrutinized. Future investigations should increase the size of respondents.

The information acquired from this study results from the need to recognize the economic significance of artisan's commitments to the improvement of the State and Nigeria overall, in spite of total neglect.

Recommendations

This study suggests as follows:

- i. Government at all levels should emplace measures to provide artisans with current apparatuses to upgrade their output.
- ii. The government should initiate policies of transferring specialized expertise and innovation from advanced economies to gifted artisans in Nigeria.
- iii. The money deposit banks should give soft advances to artisans to empower them to secure new apparatuses.
- iv. Since artisans have self-organized associations and unions, the NDE should implement measures to collect sufficient data on them in all Nigerian villages, towns, and cities to provide equipment.

Future studies should zero in on the detailed reception of a credit strategy and what web-based business means for its efficiency.

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